

Particleboards from side- and waste streams

More recently, post-consumer wood has been used as raw material for the production of particleboards. The main challenges using post-consumer wood are chemical-treated wood products such as painted or varnished materials. How can these be re-used or removed for new panel production in a profitable way? Large investments into recycling plants are needed in order to implement a recycling system on a national level. Good practice cases present well-established, advanced systems for recycling locally sourced post-consumer wood waste from demolition and municipal waste collection that can be recycled in an efficient way.

Why is it a good practice?

- ▶ Particleboards are one of the best examples of full-circle recycling within the wood working sector. Post-consumer particleboard is often recycled into new panels with great efficiency.
- ▶ From a technological point of view, almost 85% of the product can be made of recycled side-streams or waste wood. At the European level, the share of recycled wood comprises between 30 and 75% and normally includes side stream wood as well.
- ▶ The legal situation of the waste wood disposal is not well regulated at European level making regional legislation very important to waste wood collection and use. Recycling from waste wood takes place predominantly in the wood-based panel industry, this is a good practice and more favorable than energy recovery which is the main end-of-life use for waste wood today.
- ▶ Self-initiated collaboration between particleboard manufacturers, local recycling companies, organisations and municipal waste systems presents an improved waste management outcome.
- ▶ Greenhouse gas emissions from the production can be reduced significantly.

Regional coverage and transferability

Regarding the recycling of wood panels, South European countries are leading with innovations and investments into recycling plants. Location of recycling plants are depending on well-established or accessible wood collection systems.

Waste collection is predominantly not centralized in many European countries. Therefore, the highly regional and heterogeneous collection systems shall not put limitations to the geographical location. Smart and innovative technologies and systems, even for specific processing is widely transferable.

